

Prognosis of Infectious Disease Using Data Mining: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Abstract

The relentless global burden posed by infectious diseases necessitates innovative approaches to prognosis and management. This study aims to provide a more academic analysis by leveraging the power of data mining. Specifically, a bibliometric analysis is conducted to illuminate trends and patterns in the prognosis of infectious diseases. By exploring the literature landscape, this study delves into the application of data mining methodologies in this critical domain. The primary objective of this research is to identify key characteristics of scholarly output in the field, including prominent journals, citation patterns, and geographic distribution. By employing bibliometric analysis techniques, the aim is to discern trends and insights that can inform future research directions and strategic interventions.

This study used data from diverse scholarly repositories, including Scopus, Web of Science, Dimension, Lense, and PubMed. Utilising advanced visualisation tools such as VOSviewer, coupled with data analysis conducted in Microsoft Excel, the vast corpus of literature is dissected and interpreted to extract meaningful findings.

The findings reveal significant trends in the publication landscape, highlighting leading journals, prolific authors, citation networks, and the geographical distribution of research output. These insights not only shed light on the current state of the field but also offer actionable intelligence for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners.

In conclusion, this research not only contributes to advancing our understanding of infectious disease prognosis but also underscores the transformative potential of data mining methodologies in shaping the future of healthcare. By translating the findings into actionable strategies, the aim is to catalyse progress towards mitigating the impact of infectious diseases on global health.

Keywords: *bibliometric analysis, citation patterns, data mining, infectious diseases, prognosis, VOSviewer*